

Mechanism of the Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis on Cobalt Catalysts

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Studies of the co-adsorption of carbon monoxide and hydrogen on cobalt catalysts indicate the formation of carbon-hydrogen-oxygen complexes as intermediate surface species in Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. Neither these precursory steps nor the final desorption of the hydrocarbon-products can be rate-controlling in the synthesis as all these are associated with rather low activation energies. It is concluded that the penultimate step of "chain-termination" is the slow step of the process as the activation energy of the analogous reaction of hydrogenolysis of ethanol on the same catalyst is close to that of the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis.

THE Fischer-Tropsch process for the commercial synthesis of liquid hydrocarbons from water-gas, in the presence of certain transition metal catalysts (usually cobalt or iron), has provided a unique example of an industrial chemical process in which interest in the reaction mechanism grew almost *pari passu* with its technical development. The overall reaction scheme may be represented by the following equations which are distinguished by the manner in which the oxygen of CO is eliminated :

The former represents the process which occurs normally on cobalt catalysts, and the latter is what obtains an iron catalysts. In addition, olefins and higher alcohols are also formed as a result of incomplete reduction of CO and side reactions. Cobalt catalysts are usually promoted with thoria or with thoria and magnesia and supported on kieselguhr, whereas iron catalysts are "unsupported" and produced directly *in situ* from Fe_3O_4 .

The currently accepted mechanism of this reaction involves the following sequence of surface processes¹:

- (i) Chemisorption of the reactants, that of CO being more vital to the succeeding step.
- (ii) Interaction of chemisorbed CO with chemisorbed and/or molecular hydrogen to form a primary carbon-hydrogen-oxygen complex, $\text{HC}=\text{O}$, $-\text{COH}$, or HCOH .

- (iii) Interaction of the primary complex with hydrogen to form a H_2COH complex.
- (iv) Surface-condensation or surface-polymerization leading to the formation of $-\text{CH}_2$ chains and elimination of $-\text{OH}$ as water in the case of cobalt catalysts.
- (v) Chain termination.
- (vi) Desorption of the synthesized hydrocarbons.

Indications that enolic complexes were presumably formed as intermediates in Fischer-Tropsch (F.T.) synthesis were provided by Weitkamp's observation² that alcohols were invariably found among the synthesis products and by the tracer experiments of Kummer *et al*³ in which it was found that the carbon moieties of alcohols added to the synthesis gas got "incorporated" in the hydrocarbon products.

Mixed adsorption of CO and hydrogen on cobalt catalysts

Information on the interaction between the chemisorbed reactants and on the surface-complex formed thereby could be obtained more directly by a study of the co-adsorption of the reactants from their binary mixtures under various conditions. Such studies were initiated by Ghosh, Sastri and their co-workers^{4,5,6} on cobalt catalysts at temperatures ranging from room temperature to about 100°C ; this upper limit of temperature was chosen to preclude occurrence of the F.T. reaction which would complicate the adsorption measurements.

These studies were facilitated by the use of a thermal conductivity meter built into the adsorption apparatus to determine the gas-composition in the system *in situ*.

On all the cobalt catalysts studied, it was found that at the higher temperatures, usually above 60°C, the amounts of either component adsorbed from the mixtures were greater than those from the respective pure gases instead of being less as would be expected normally on account of competition between the adsorbates for the available sites. This mutual enhancement which, it was observed recently⁷, was reflected in the rates of adsorption also, could be attributed to the following causes :

- (i) Increased activity of the catalyst surface *per se* due to a cooperative work function effect arising from the chemisorbed CO and H species forming oppositely charged dipoles ($\text{CO}^{\delta-}$ and $\text{H}^{\delta+}$) on the surface, thereby altering the work function of the metal in opposite ways and reducing the electronic barriers to the adsorption of both the gases.
- (ii) Attractive interaction between the chemisorbed CO and H dipoles, without complex formation. This also would give the effect of enhanced activity of the surface for the adsorption of either gas.
- (iii) Chemical interaction on the catalyst surface between chemisorbed CO and H species (Langmuir-Hinshelwood type) or between chemisorbed CO and gaseous hydrogen or *vice versa* (Rideal type) leading to the formation of chemisorbed surface complexes, such as HCO or COH.
- (iv) Chemical interaction of the primary surface complex (HCO or COH) with chemisorbed or gaseous hydrogen to give rise progressively to HCOH and H_2COH complexes. This would account mainly for enhancement of hydrogen-adsorption.

Of the above, the most potent causes of mutual enhancement and the ones most relevant to the reaction mechanism are the last two.

At temperatures below 50°C, however, the mutual retardation effects of competitive adsorption prevailed over the enhancement effects enumerated above.

This indicated that the chemical interactions between (or with) the adsorbed species were associated with an appreciable activation energy restraining their occurrence at lower temperatures. The same cannot be said about the work-function effect and dipole attractions, because these are rarely temperature-dependent

Composition of the intermediate surface-complex

In two recent papers^{7,8} the present authors have described how the technique of mixed adsorption measurements could be used to determine the composition of the adsorbed (CO, H_2) complex and to study the kinetics of its formation and transformation. These studies were carried out on two standard cobalt Fischer-Tropsch catalysts having the compositions, Co : ThO_2 : Kieselguhr = 100 : 18 : 200 and Co : ThO_2 : MgO : Kieselguhr = 100 : 6 : 12 : 200, by weight. The catalyst with the latter composition was found to possess greater stability of activity than the former on repeated exposure to CO- H_2 mixtures followed by high temperature regeneration. Otherwise, both catalysts exhibited practically the same general behaviour in mixed adsorption. The results obtained with both these catalysts indicated that exposure to a 1:1 CO- H_2 mixture produced at about 80°C a primary surface complex of the composition H_2CO (presumably HCOH) which at higher temperatures underwent facile hydrogenation to H_2COH . The composite adsorbed phase formed at temperatures below 80°C was relatively rich in CO, presumably due to the presence of free, i.e., uncombined, chemisorbed CO, in addition to some CO- H_2 complex, on the surface. Exposure to 1:2 CO- H_2 mixture yielded surface-compositions which were richer in hydrogen than those obtained with the 1:1 mixture, the difference being particularly marked at higher temperatures ($\geq 80^\circ$), but negligible at lower temperatures ($< 60^\circ$).

Rate-determining step in Fischer-Tropsch synthesis

(a) Precursor complex formation

Rate-measurements were made of the individual steps leading to the formation of the primary surface-complex (H_2CO) and its interaction with hydrogen on the Co- ThO_2 -MgO-kieselguhr catalyst. The activation energies calculated therefrom are given in Table 1. All these values are too low compared with the value of 25 kcal/mole reported by Anderson *et al.*⁹ for the overall activation energy of Fischer-Tropsch synthesis on a catalyst of the same composition.

TABLE 1—ACTIVATION ENERGIES OF PRE-REACTION STEPS IN FISCHER-TROPSCH SYNTHESIS ON Co-ThO₂-MgO-KIESELGUHR CATALYST

Process	Temperature range (°C)	Activation Energy Kcal/mole
1. Chemisorption of CO	56—100	~ 0.5
2. Chemisorption of H ₂	56—100	~ 0.75
3. Interaction of H ₂ (g) with chemisorbed CO	80—100	7.4
4. Interaction of H ₂ (g) with chemisorbed (CO, H ₂) complex formed by contacting catalyst with 1:1 CO-H ₂ mixture at 80°C.	80—100	3.3

Hence, none of these processes can be rate-determining in the overall synthesis reaction.

(b) *Desorption of hydrocarbon products*

To see if the desorption of the synthesis products could be rate-determining, as suggested by Anderson¹⁰, the adsorption isotherms of n-pentane, n-hexane, n-heptane and n-octane were determined at four temperatures between 150° and 210°C (the temperature range of active synthesis) on the Co-ThO₂-MgO-kieselguhr catalyst using the gas-chromatographic technique¹¹, which is particularly suitable and convenient for the study of adsorption of vapours. The isothermic heats of adsorption deduced from these isotherms using the Claypeyron equation for a coverage of 4.4 micromoles per gram of catalyst were 5.17, 6.89, 8.15, 8.24 kcal/mole respectively for the C₅, C₆, C₇ and C₈ n-paraffins. These values are fairly close to the heats of liquefaction of the same hydrocarbons, namely, 6.27, 6.84, 7.65 and 8.10 kcal/mole, showing thereby that the hydrocarbons are physically adsorbed on the catalyst. Since no activation energy is involved in physical adsorption, the activation energies of desorption should be reckoned as numerically equal to the heats of adsorption. These are obviously too low for the desorption of products to be rate determining in F.T. synthesis.

(c) *Surface-polymerization and chain termination*

Finally, we are left with surface-polymerization (or homologation) and chain-termination to be

examined for the slow-step in F.T. synthesis. The former involves a condensation reaction between neighbouring enolic complexes on the surface, with elimination of water, followed eventually by chain-termination, thus :

(a) *Condensation*

and so on.

(b) *Chain termination*

These together constitute the vital step in F.T. synthesis and, indeed, one that distinguishes the latter from other simpler reactions of CO and hydrogen, such as, methanation and methanol synthesis. Of the two processes, chain termination will be the slower one, since otherwise methane will be the principal product rather than higher hydrocarbons. Since it is not possible experimentally to isolate this step in a regular synthesis reaction, the kinetics of a closely analogous reaction, namely, the hydrogenolysis of ethanol,

was studied on the Co-ThO₂-MgO-kieselguhr catalyst at nine temperatures between 150 and 230°C, employing the gas-chromatographic technique¹² in which the catalyst substituted for the column material.

A meter length of 1/4" O.D. copper tubing was packed uniformly with 6.05 g of the unreduced catalyst-granules (20 mesh), coiled and fitted into a Varian Aerograph Model A-90-P3 single column gas-chromatograph, which was provided with a thermal conductivity detector. The catalyst was reduced

in situ by passing a rapid stream of pure dry electrolytic hydrogen for over 12 hours at 350°C. The column-oven temperature was then adjusted to stabilize at the desired reaction-temperature and the flow of hydrogen (which served both as reactant and carrier-gas) maintained at 90 ml per minute. The reaction was initiated by injecting 5 μ l of pure dry ethanol (purity checked by GC). The two peaks which appeared in the chromatogram were identified as due to ethane and ethanol+water. It was confirmed independently that (i) water was reversibly adsorbed when injected into the hydrogen steam and (ii) water and ethanol could not be separated by the catalyst-column. The reaction had therefore to be monitored entirely with the yield of ethane.

The results of these experiments are presented in Table 2. The plot of logarithm of the ethane-peak area vs $1/T$ yielded a straight line the slope of which gave a value of 19.0 kcal/mole for the activation energy of the reaction.

TABLE 2—YIELD OF ETHANE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temperature (°C)	Ethane peak area
153	87
159	109
173	238
182	299
193	564
198	620
209	871
220	1440
238	2102

Attempts were made to evaluate the apparent activation energy of the surface-polymerization and chain-termination steps together from the amounts of water formed when synthesis gas ($1\text{CO}+2\text{H}_2$) was passed over the catalyst at different temperatures. However, these attempts were not successful since the

product-distribution varied with variations of reactant space velocity and catalyst-temperature and, consequently, the yield of water at constant contact time varied erratically with temperature. The only fruitful outcome of these experiments was that the percentage contraction of the synthesis gas (indicating the extent of conversion) at different temperatures but same space velocity (1000 hr^{-1}) returned a value of 24 kcal/mole for the overall activation energy of the F.T. synthesis, in close agreement with that reported earlier⁹ in literature.

Conclusion : The activation energy of the chain termination step may be taken as the same as that of the ethanol-hydrogenolysis reaction, namely, 19.0 kcal/mole, since basically both involve the same molecular transformation. When comparing this value with the overall activation energy of the F.T. synthesis, it may be noted that the gas-chromatographic reactor technique is known to give slightly lower values for the activation energy than those determined by conventional methods. Thus, Gaziev *et al*¹³ observed that for the dehydrogenation of cyclohexane the activation energy found by the chromatographic method was 3 kcal/mole less than that obtained with the static reactor, while Roginskii¹⁴ provided general theoretical support for such observations. Allowing for this difference in activation energy arising from the use of the chromatographic technique, the activation energy of the chain termination reaction may be admitted as comparable to the overall activation energy of the F.T. reaction. This leads us to the important conclusion that chain-termination by hydrogenolysis of the polymerized enolic surface complexes constitutes the rate determining step in Fischer-Tropsch synthesis of hydrocarbons over cobalt catalysts.

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